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**Roles of Financial Independence and
Community Involvement in Enhancing
the Quality of Life among Retired
Individuals**

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Abstract

Retirement, a significant transition in life, often presents retirees with challenges such as the loss of working identity, reduced income, and the adjustment to new routines. Financial independence and community involvement are essential factors that can enhance the quality of life in retirement. This study examines the role of these two factors in retirees' well-being, dignity, and life satisfaction. Using a qualitative approach, this research employs descriptive analysis to explore how financial security and active social engagement impact retirees' overall quality of life. The study is grounded in two key theoretical frameworks: the Life Course Theory, which emphasizes the long-term effects of financial decisions on retirement, and the Activity Theory of Aging, which underscores the importance of maintaining social engagement after retirement for improved mental and emotional health. Through an extensive review of literature and analysis of empirical data, the study investigates how financial independence and community involvement collectively contribute to

retirees' life satisfaction. Findings from this research inform practical recommendations for retirees, caregivers, and policy-makers, emphasizing the importance of early financial planning and fostering active community participation. Governments and private employers should support retirees through planning workshops, post-retirement job opportunities, and improved access to healthcare and social welfare. Additionally, strengthening community-based support networks and encouraging social engagement can help retirees stay active, included, and mentally fulfilled. These insights aim to provide a holistic approach to ensuring that retirement is not only financially secure but also socially fulfilling, leading to improved quality of life.

Keywords: Retirement, Financial Independence, Community Involvement, Quality of Life

Introduction

Retirement is one of the most important transitions in people's life. It is a new phase of life in which a lot of changes happen in individuals (Swedroe & Grogan, 2021; Rønnow, Smed & Tetens, 2024). It is like a new adventure into which some people are even afraid to enter. The fear comes mainly from three realities in which retired people face: losing one's working identity, living on a fixed income and adapting to a new routine. During one's career, an individual is exposed to many activities making up a pleasing life. One's work offers them a sense of purpose. They are strengthened by the self-esteem achieved because they are good at activities they do, and others recognise it. Besides, a person reaches a certain level of financial security. They are happy and matured by the relationships they have with colleagues (Swedroe & Grogan, 2021). With retirement, everything provided by one's career vanishes. Hence, it is very important to plan for it since it also determines the quality of life one will live out. Whether one is in retirement already or planning to retire in some years, the most important thing is to take time to reflect on what sort of life one wants to live out in one's later years. For most individuals, retirement makes up the best years of their lives. For the first time in decades, they are usually free. It is a period in which one has time to enjoy favourite pastimes and hobbies, with loved ones and be there for them in a way that was not possible while working, and time to just explore oneself and the things to be involved in. Whatever this may be, it's worth taking time to think about what one wants to do (Howard,

2021). Retirement from active life may be rough or smooth, thereby affecting one's quality of life (Afthanorhan, Mamun, Zainol, Foziyah & Awang, 2020). It is important to know that retirement is, for most, an absorbing stage starting at the mid-60s and lasting until death. The lifestyle changes may have several implications that can affect life related behaviour (Rønnow, Smed & Tetens, 2024). Note that retirement may last more than thirty years. So, it is well worth taking time to reflect upon how to spend that time. The latter will have several phases. One is active in the first 10 or 20 years than in the later years and should plan well around it. It is possible to stay in the workforce longer by continuing to do what one was doing before, perhaps on a part-time basis, or changing to something completely different (Howard, 2021). The reality about retirement is that most people have issues with their financial resources and their income decreases substantially (Rønnow, Smed & Tetens, 2024). Besides studies show that the bigger number of divorces is among couples over 55 years old. This is because they start to reflect on how they will live together during retirement (Swedroe & Grogan, 2021). Hence, a significant number of retirees experience a diminished quality of life, primarily due to inadequate financial resources and limited social engagement.

This study aims to explore the role of financial independence and community involvement in enhancing the quality of life among retired individuals. Specifically, it seeks to examine how financial security and active social engagement contribute to retirees' overall well-being, sense of dignity, and life satisfaction. The central research question guiding this inquiry is: How do financial independence and community involvement collectively influence the quality of life among retired individuals? A qualitative approach will be employed, utilizing descriptive analysis to assess how financial independence and community engagement enhance the quality of life among retirees. The study shall be underpinned by a well-defined theoretical framework and an extensive review of existing literature. The findings will be discussed in depth, and practical recommendations will be offered based on the analysis

Theoretical Framework

To understand how financial independence and community involvement enhance the quality of life among retirees, there are two key theories that

provide the foundation: the Life Course Theory and Activity Theory of Aging. The Life Course Theory, as coined by Glen H. Elder Jr. in 1974, offers a solid basis to understand how financial independence impacts the quality of life among retirees. This theory stresses that “what happens in one period of a person’s life is connected to what happens in other periods of that person’s life” (Hutchison, 2019). According to this view, people who make the right financial decisions during their career enjoy a happy retirement, free from financial stress and anxiety. The Life Course Theory indicates also that social and historical contexts shape financial occasions (Holman & Walker, 2021). Besides, the Activity Theory of Aging, developed by Havighurst & Albrecht in 1953, complements the Life Course theory by highlighting the importance of community involvement in increasing retirees’ wellbeing. It points out that maintaining an active social life and engaging in meaningful activities after retirement lead to improved mental health, higher life satisfaction, and overall wellbeing (Lemon, Bengtson & Peterson, 1972). All in all, the two theories provide a holistic understanding of how financial independence (Life Course Theory), and social engagement (Activity Theory) contribute to enhance the quality of life among retirees.

Literature Review

Notion of Quality of Life

Quality of life implies the degree to which somebody is happy, fit, and capable to enjoy and participate in life happenings. *As a concept, quality of life* is essentially vague, since it can denote both an individual’s life or the experience he or she has and the living conditions in which people find themselves (Stimson, Marans & Webster, 2024). Thus, quality of life is very subjective: while an individual may define it according to life satisfaction or wealth, another one may refer to it in terms of capabilities (living a good life in terms of physical and emotional wellbeing). For instance, a person with disability may indicate to have a high quality of life, while a healthy individual who have recently lost his job shows a low quality of life. Note that academic attention on quality of life started to grow after the Second World War, when there was increasing recognition and awareness of social inequalities (Jenkinson, 2024). Besides, quality of life, as a multidimensional concept, aims at capturing the wellness, whether of an individual or a population, as regards both positive and negative aspects

within the entirety of existence at a specific point in time (Teoli & Bhardwaj, 2022).

Retirement and Quality of Life

Retirement opens the door to a range of new activities that one may have always wanted to know more about but never had time for (Howard, 2021). It is important to note that there are two pathways to retirement at an advance age: early voluntary retirement at the age of 60 and standard retirement at age 65. People are free to choose anytime between ages 60 and 65. To be able to qualify for the early voluntary retirement pension, there are some conditions which must be met. Aspirants should be members of an unemployment fund and must have contributed for at least 30 years. In this way, part time work is permitted, although the pension amount is adjusted based on working hours and earnings. Besides, people may choose to delay their pension to continue working; this could result in a higher pension payment after retirement (Rønnow, Smed & Tetens, 2024). After all, for a person to enjoy the retirement, it necessitates training, planning, and counselling; having in mind that it is a period characterised by changes in people's mental, economic, social, nutritional and health state. Therefore, employees should find approaches for dealing with their post-retirement lives, to remain healthy and productive after active responsibility, regardless of unfavourable and tough conditions. On the side of government, there is a need of improving investment opportunities, training and skill development, preparation for acquisition, consciousness campaign through seminars, workshops and public talks in preparation for retirement (Oloso, 2022).

Accessed in the context of psychological wellbeing, the quality of life is critical especially during the time of retirement for the fact that all the human needs in individuals are not met as one could wish. The retiree may not be prepared enough for this new step of life changes. Many scholars have indicated that psychological preparedness is very important and determines the quality of life among the retirees (Jais & Asokumar, 2020). Retirement has been compared to a longest vacation a person may take after many years of service. Consequently, it is crucial to commence thinking about it as soon as an individual starts any kind of productive employment or labour production (Oloso, 2022). Planning for retirement is all about starting the process of deciding ahead of time, what is to be done, how it will be done to

attain anticipated goals. This includes putting in place objectives and drawing activities to be accomplished, establishing policies and sequencing procedures that will guide programmes implementation for the attainment of given aims (Eboh & Agabi, 2021).

Planning for a Smooth Retirement

All about life necessitates planning. Life itself entails planning, so also retirement. The latter ought to be prepared early. This aids workers to identify means and procedures to be adopted to augment likelihoods of enjoying a relaxed life after service. Thus, creating retirement consciousness and enlightening employees on subjects that have to do with planning (including investment and savings) is an essential way of helping workers' attitude towards sustainably paving a way for active immersion in preparation processes (Eboh & Agabi, 2021). These are meant to make life enjoyable when an individual leaves active duty. It has been confirmed that an employee who neglects retirement preparations is likely to run the danger of facing some difficulties that arise after retirement (Oloso, 2022). Hence, post-retirement preparation is not only late but also risky, since it makes the workers to be in a disadvantaged position whereby preparation is much more challenging. Beginning retirement planning on time helps to get adequate information about pension funds management, investment opportunities, strategies, company's products (pension arrangements) that outfits their specific income levels. Preparing retirement in advance helps as well to plan how to live within one's means (Eboh & Agabi, 2021).

Failing to plan for retirement leads to unnecessary risks in one's old age, including poor health, frustration, low self-esteem, unemployment, low socio-economic status, to mention but a few (Oloso, 2022). Most of the time, when an individual is employed in civil service and appointed in public offices in Nigeria for instance, there is a period of orientation and induction programmes meant to familiarize the new workers with their new roles and work routines. During this time, the emphasis is mainly on work and performance discussions; nothing is said about the retirement. It is the same thing during in-service trainings; emphasis is rarely given to matters concerning employees' retirement planning. Hence, many workers are not aware about issues related to retirement preparation (Eboh & Agabi, 2021).

Consequence of Poor Planning for Retirement

In a study investigating on retirement planning awareness and planning options among university staffs, it is revealed that university personnel are very much involved in their retirement planning activities. It was found that the senior non-teaching workers were more involved in their retirement preparation than teaching and junior non-teaching staff (Eboh & Agabi, 2021). Studies have shown that people who psychologically plan for their retirement adapts better than those who improvise. Hence, retirees who fail to prepare for their retirement on time, their quality of life is affected after service (Kiyiapi, Gacohi, & Omondi, 2023). They may succumb form mental related issues and may struggle to manage life after retirement. Since it is the best way to ensure a comfortable, safe and joyful retirement, planning for it ought to start on time.

In each country, there are some organizations in charge of retirement benefit provision and planning which, in places with working pension systems, make retirees to live happily on their pension benefits. In the case of Nigeria, the National Pension Commission (PENCOM), in charge of the activities of both pension fund administrators and pension asset custodians in the overall benefit of retirees, takes care of this. However, there are two challenges among retirees in Nigeria: retirement income loses value easily due to inflation making life difficult for the senior citizens and the pension payments are constantly paid late due to bureaucracy and corruption. These have severe effects on the pensioners because regardless of their health, they should undergo a series of examinations in which they ought to be present. They need to travel long distance for verification (Oloso, 2022). Hence the working systems of any organization taking care of retirement benefit provision should always aim for the wellbeing of retirees.

Discussion of Findings

Financial Independence and Quality of Life in Retirement

Financial factors are integral to maintaining a high quality of life in retirement, as overall well-being extends beyond fulfilling basic needs and is closely tied to financial stability. Early and effective financial planning, initiated during one's career, is essential in addressing the challenges faced after retirement, thereby supporting both independence and long-term sustainability.

- *Financial Considerations for Post-Retirement Wellbeing*

Quality of life is connected to financial factors outside the basic needs of shelter and food. During the life of service, the availability of money gives access to greater freedom from anxieties, comfort, and an optimistic outlook for the future (Kagan, 2024). However, one day after retirement celebration, every advantage provided by one's career is gone. He or she must find other ways to rebuild a daily, weekly, and yearly structure and to replace the intellectual stimulation that so readily came from work (Swedroe & Grogan, 2021). This is the reason why the ideal time to begin planning for retirement is the very first month one starts earning the first salary (Ibeme, 2014). It is important to note that the quality of pre-retirement financial plan is affected by certain personal factors including one's salary and family size, while realities such as economic changes, salary increases or decreases, competency of pension funds guardians and administrators may affect retirement financial preparations (Eboh & Agabi, 2021). These involve setting aside a portion of one's income or resources specifically for retirement. The primary goal of retirement planning is to reach financial independence, making employment a choice rather than a requirement. Unfortunately, some individuals find themselves troubled with heavy debt during retirement; they face challenges which include building savings, paying monthly bills, sustaining their lifestyle, or funding their children's education and so on (Ibeme, 2014).

- *Financial Responsibilities and Investment Strategies*

During retirement, it is necessary to be careful in the use of money. Every cent should be spent after valid reasons. As for starting any kind of business either for small or big investments, one should seek for good advice from experts. These will help to clarify certain things that may not seem to be obvious as one plans to set up any kind of investment. This should not be started after retirement when life depends on pension savings made during the time of active duties (Howard, 2021). In addition, economic possessions accessible for individuals have been identified as essential for retirement decisions and timing. For some people, the decision and timing of retirement depend only on regular old age pension benefits and income transfers bridging the gap between the exit from work and entry into regular old age pension schemes (Sjöberg, 2022). The employers should assist their employees by giving them opportunities to attend pre-

retirement seminars at least five years before they are due to retire. It can be an occasion for the intending retirees to discover on what to look forward to in the time of retirement, its challenges and realities. They will likewise be taught and well educated on the forms of businesses and how to register for them. They as well need to be informed on how they can generate their own business concepts, how to put down business proposals, source for start-up capital for commerce, as well as how to begin and manage a business (Ibeme, 2014). Hence, after one has built a business, they can decide to retire or withdraw from actual career without worry.

- Financial Discipline for Retirement Success

Future financial independence depends on the exercise of present financial discipline (Goidel, 2023). It is important to learn how to invest right form the time of employment. Scholars recommend starting investment already in one's 20s, or soon after obtaining the very first full-time job. Regularly, it is advisable to contribute to one's retirement account to the maximum amount allowed, considering one's living expenses. With time in one's 30s, it is good to build a reserve fund that may cover at least six months of living expenses in case of incapability to work or joblessness. Anything can happen in life. This is the reason why it is good at this stage of life to consider purchasing disability insurance. It is during this time that normally people enter into marriage. During the 40s, one may contemplate saving for the children's studies and assisting aging parents. And in the 50s and 60s, as far as one is still working, they try to save for all the priorities and maximize the investment before retiring (Goidel, 2023). To be independent financially during retirement depends mainly on how one has been disciplined in their lifestyle and spending.

Community Involvement and Quality of Life

During retirement, community involvement plays a vital role in increasing the quality of life by encouraging social engagement. This is done through partaking in activities such as hobbies, leisure, household works and volunteering. However, the priority is to adjust to new social roles.

- Adjustment to New Social Roles

Retirement is a life-changing period, due to the necessity of adjusting to new social roles, connected to acquisition of a new perspective and increasing the

amount of free time, which can be used to fulfil needs and aspirations that were neglected previously (Kalbarczyk, & Łopaciuk-Gonczaryk, 2022). Transition into retirement can be understood based on role theory. The latter is one of the important theories in retirement and social aging. The role theory proposes that a key to successful retirement is to continue engaging in significant activities and roles that give a person joy, a sense of identity and purpose. Hence people who maintain active participation in social and occupational roles after retirement are more likely to experience a better quality of life. Role theory focuses on the importance of community involvements such as one's roles and responsibilities. These include being a volunteer, worker, grandparents, to name but a few. As people retire, they intend to lose their social roles and responsibilities leading them to social isolation (Freund, 2020). It is good to adjust by keeping themselves busy, helping people round them with their long-life experience. In that sense, retirement gives an opportunity for participation in family life and activities benefiting the community at large.

- *Hobbies, Leisure and Household Activities*

To engage in hobbies, leisure and household activities is the best option to substitute for career work, promoting a sense of continuity as one enters into the adjustment to retirement (Henning, Stenling, Bielak, Bjälkebring, Gow, Kivi, Muniz-Terrera, Johansson & Lindwall, 2021). Encouraging such activities among individuals who are coming out of their career may help to maintain their health after transition (Lee, Chi & Ailshire, 2020). They are associated to higher levels of quality of life and lower levels of functional limitations, depressive symptoms, mortality and cognitive impairment (Lee, Chi & Ailshire, 2020). Also, hobbies, leisure and household activities are linked to a better physical, mental and cognitive health among the retirees and workers (Ortak & Bulut, 2022). They include all “activities that involve social interaction with family, friends, peers, and other members of society resulting in mutual social interaction” (Zhang, Zhou & Jiang, 2022). Continuity theory is another theory claiming that retirees would like to continue in the most important aspects of their pre-retirement lives. Hobbies, leisure and household activities should help to maintain such aspects of post-retirement life including social contacts, cognitive stimulation and self-respect (Henning, Stenling, Bielak, Bjälkebring, Gow, Kivi, Muniz-Terrera, Johansson, & Lindwall, 2021).

- Voluntary Work

Retirees and those approaching retirement ought to start increasing their commitment in voluntary work as they leave their paid work. Still, across the lifespan some people have multifaceted inspirations for volunteering, such as career improvement, self-fulfilment, to name but a few. Many volunteers combine their career work and volunteering during young adulthood and middle age (Eibich, Lorenti & Mosca, 2022). Volunteering after retirement is associated with better health and well-being and is thus considered part of an “active ageing” strategy. It is increasingly being promoted as an important aspect of retirement planning, since it provides people opportunities to gain knowledge, remain active, contribute to their skills, and leave a lasting impact for future generations (Sladowski & Hientz, 2010). Volunteer work during retirement includes people’s engagement in unpaid works benefiting the community and at the same time providing self-fulfilment. It helps retirees to remain active, keep social connections, and keep using their experience and skills in more significant ways. Volunteer work has common forms including tutoring, mentoring, and so on.

Conclusion

From the foregoing, the quality of life encompasses various aspects contributing to the overall wellbeing among retirees such as physical health (mobility, managing chronic illnesses, etc.), psychological wellbeing (emotional stability, a sense of purpose and coping with changes) and social engagement (keeping relationships, remaining active in the community and volunteer work). The quality of life among the retirees is enhanced by financial independence and community involvement. The first allows the retirees to be autonomous, feel secured and dignity, reducing anxiety and stress related to economic instability. With financial independence, retirees have access to health care, leisure activities and proper nutrition contributing to an enjoyable life.

Recommendations

The following are some recommendations for enhancing the quality of life among the retirees:

1. Governments and private employers should provide workshops and resources to help people plan better for their retirement.

2. Post-retirement job opportunities should be encouraged among the retirees such as consultancy, part-time work and entrepreneurship for them to remain financially independent while socially and mentally engaged.
3. A community-based social support networks should be strengthened. This may be done in creating clubs for senior citizens, volunteer work programmes to foster social inclusion and prevent loneliness.
4. Community engagement ought to be encouraged, offering possibilities for retirees to contribute meaningfully to the society with their long-life experience.
5. Governments should enhance access to affordable healthcare and social welfare for retirees.

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International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health 19(8):
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